
CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK / THEORETICAL MODEL

**“Forced Expulsion through “Release”.
A Structural Form of Repression under
the Limits of International Protection”.**

A Methodological Concept
for the Identification and Verification
of a Non-Classical Repressive Practice

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Methodological Concept

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Analytical framework for identifying and verifying a specific form of repression not covered by classical legal categories such as deportation, expulsion, or voluntary migration.

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This concept develops and formalizes the analytical findings presented in the report “Release Without Freedom: Forced Expulsion of Political Prisoners and Legal Vacuum in the Republic of Belarus” (20 December 2025) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18444848>.

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Executive Summary

This concept introduces and systematizes the phenomenon of forced expulsion through “release” as an independent form of repressive practice not covered by classical legal categories such as deportation, expulsion, or voluntary departure. Within this phenomenon, release from places of deprivation of liberty is used by the regime not to end repression and restore the individual’s legal status, but as an instrument for the physical removal of the person beyond the borders of the state, without adopting a decision on expulsion and without terminating criminal prosecution.

A key feature of this practice is the absence of any real and safe alternative for the “released” person to continue life within the country. The termination of deprivation of liberty is not accompanied by the formalization of a completed legal status, security guarantees, or access to effective protection mechanisms. In the basic configuration of the phenomenon, refusal to leave leads to the immediate resumption of isolation and the de facto disappearance of the person from the legal and informational space. As a result, expulsion beyond the borders of the state acquires the character of a forced and the only available scenario for ending pressure.

This practice demonstrates a distortion of the logic of the legal completion of punishment: a repressive measure begins to be perceived as less destructive compared to refusing it, which undermines the basic principle of the legal finality of punishment.

The concept demonstrates that this mechanism operates under conditions marking the limits of applicability of both domestic and international human rights protection mechanisms. Within a repressive regime, law does not perform a protective function for individuals in political conflict with the state, while international mechanisms are unable to ensure physical security and legal certainty on the territory of a state that does not permit external oversight. Under these conditions, protection of the individual becomes possible only after their actual expulsion beyond the borders of the state.

Within the framework of the concept, the key features of the phenomenon, the mechanism of its reproduction, as well as criteria for verification and logical refutation are systematized. The proposed analytical model makes it possible to distinguish forced expulsion through “release” from other forms of movement of persons and to identify it on the basis of objective consequences rather than statements by the regime or external interpretations.

At present, the phenomenon has been recorded in a single basic configuration that has formed under the conditions of the Belarusian regime and demonstrates the most severe form of its implementation. This configuration is used in the concept as the initial analytical reference point and a scale for possible subsequent comparative analysis in other political and legal contexts.

Introduction

In 2025, a stable repressive practice was recorded in the Republic of Belarus that had not previously been described in human rights or legal analysis as an independent mechanism. This practice concerns situations in which individuals deprived of liberty on political grounds are removed from places of detention without the establishment of a completed legal status and are forcibly expelled beyond the borders of the state.

The first episodes of this practice were implemented within a short period of time - on 21 June, 11 September, and 13 December 2025. Their chronological proximity, similarity of conditions, and identity of outcomes make it possible to regard these events not as a set of isolated incidents, but as the formation of a stable and reproducible mechanism of repressive impact.

A defining feature of the recorded practice is the use of release from places of detention as a stage of immediate forced expulsion. Within this mechanism, release does not signify the termination of repression and is not accompanied by the restoration of the individual's legal status.

Remaining within the country after release is not permitted: refusal to leave leads to the immediate resumption of isolation and the effective disappearance of the individual from the legal and public sphere. Thus, release is used not as the restoration of freedom, but as a technical element of direct forced expulsion beyond the territory of the state.

The emergence of this practice is linked not to a change in the objectives of the repressive regime, but to changes in the political and diplomatic conditions under which those objectives are pursued. In contemporary conditions, open forms of repression - such as formally documented expulsion or deportation - have become politically and diplomatically costly. Under these circumstances, repressive impact is transformed, shifting beyond the state's territory and taking forms that do not leave customary legal traces.

At the same time, the limits of applicability of both domestic and international human rights protection mechanisms become evident. Within a repressive regime, law does not perform a protective function for individuals who are in political conflict with the state, while international mechanisms are unable to ensure physical security and legal certainty within the territory of a state that does not allow external oversight. Under these conditions, protection of the individual becomes possible only after their actual expulsion beyond the borders of the state.

The use of release as an externally neutral action, as well as the emphasis on mediation and the organization of departure, contributed to the fact that the coercive nature of expulsion and the absence of any alternative to remaining inside the country long remained outside systematic analytical documentation and human rights qualification. The phenomenon becomes visible not through the analysis of individual actions by the regime, but through examination of the structure of available alternatives after "release" and the regime's response to refusal to be expelled.

As a result, a paradoxical situation emerges: a repressive measure begins to be perceived as less destructive than the refusal of it. This, in turn, blurs the understanding of punishment as a legally completed and predictable form of state action.

This concept proceeds from the analysis of this basic configuration and is aimed at introducing forced expulsion through "release" as an independent analytical category, necessary for the accurate description and assessment of this form of repressive practice.

1. Initial Logic of the Phenomenon

The phenomenon of forced expulsion through release arises at the moment when release from places of deprivation of liberty is used by the state as a means of immediate forced removal of a person beyond the borders of the country without the adoption of a decision on expulsion.

Within this mechanism, release does not signify the termination of repression. The person's presence within the country after release is not permitted: refusal to leave leads to the immediate resumption of isolation and the factual disappearance of the person from the legal and public space.

Thus, release is used not as the restoration of freedom, but as a technical stage of direct forced expulsion beyond the territory of the state.

This concept is based on the only currently documented precedent - the Belarusian configuration of the phenomenon, which is geographically singular but systematic in the practice of this regime. In this case, forced expulsion through release is implemented in an extremely rigid form: the released person is not afforded the possibility to remain within the country; refusal to leave results in the immediate resumption of isolation and the disappearance of the person from the legal and public space.

2. Origin of the Phenomenon: Conditions and Preconditions

The phenomenon of forced expulsion through release is not an accidental occurrence. Its emergence is linked not to a change in the objectives of repressive regimes, but to a change in the conditions under which those objectives are implemented.

In contemporary authoritarian regimes, overt forms of repression - such as officially formalized expulsion, deportation, or forced displacement - have become politically and diplomatically costly. They require the formal adoption of decisions, leave direct documentary traces, facilitate external legal qualification of violations, and quickly become objects of external pressure.

Under these conditions, regimes seek to preserve repressive control while avoiding actions that are directly recorded as expulsion.

As a result, repression assumes a different form. Release is used not as a return of the person to life within the country, but as a means of immediate forced removal beyond the borders of the state without the adoption of a decision on expulsion.

Release loses its independent significance and becomes part of a mechanism of direct forced expulsion, in which the individual is physically removed from the territory of the country without the formalization of expulsion as a legal act.

2.1. Transition from Direct Coercion to Structural Repression

Classical forms of repression were based on the direct action of the regime within the state. Deprivation of liberty, expulsion, and forced displacement were carried out through official decisions and administrative acts that could be documented and qualified within legal categories. Such repression was visible and easily recognizable.

In the contemporary international environment, such actions are associated for regimes with high risks and consequences. They create stable grounds for external reaction, lead to sanctions, political pressure, and deterioration of the international position. This does not imply an abandonment of repression, but it limits the possibility of its open application.

In response to these constraints, repressive impact is shifted beyond the borders of the state. Release is used as a mechanism for the immediate physical removal of a person from the territory of the country without formalizing expulsion as an independent decision.

Coercion is implemented not through the provision of alternatives, but through the elimination of the very possibility for the person to remain within the country after release.

2.2. “Release” as a New Phase of Repression

Within the framework of the phenomenon under consideration, the term “release” is used in a distorted sense and does not signify the termination of repressive impact, but rather represents one of the forms of its continuation. For this reason, the word “release” is used exclusively in quotation marks throughout this concept.

Such “release” does not return the individual to a protected legal space and does not create conditions for safe residence within the country. It does not restore legal status, but instead performs a different function within the structure of repressive impact.

Within the examined practice, “release” is used as a technical transitional stage in which repression does not cease, but is replaced by another form of repressive impact - the forced removal of the individual beyond the territory of the state without formalizing expulsion as a legal act.

2.3. Destruction of the Internal Protection Mechanism

The key premise of this phenomenon lies in the fact that the regime does not initially provide for legal protection for individuals who are in political conflict with it. In such cases, law is not designed to protect and cannot perform this function.

The objective of the regime is to create conditions under which dissent becomes impossible. Within this logic, any formal procedures - courts, lawyers, complaints, petitions - do not function as instruments of protection. They exist not to prevent arbitrary actions by the regime, but to exercise control, exert pressure, and eliminate individuals regarded as politically disloyal.

After “release,” the individual remains within a system that does not recognize their right to safety. The possibility of remaining in the country and “defending oneself legally” in such conditions is excluded by definition: for a person in conflict with the regime, there is no institutionally protected legal space within the country in which their safety and status could be guaranteed.

Refusal of expulsion and an attempt to remain inside the country under the conditions of the practice in question formally constitute an act of choice. However, this choice lacks the substantive characteristics of freedom: it is not accompanied by any guarantees of safety, legal certainty, or predictability of consequences.

In practice, refusal of expulsion means a transition into a state of complete uncertainty, in which the individual’s further fate cannot be verified. Their whereabouts, legal status, and even the very fact of their continued existence cease to be accessible to legal documentation and public oversight. The individual does not return to any formalized procedure - they disappear from the institutionally observable legal and public space.

This logic is not hypothetical. Within the Belarusian configuration of the phenomenon, cases have been documented in which refusal of expulsion resulted in the complete disappearance of the individual from the public and legal sphere. Thus, following his refusal to leave the country in September 2025, the whereabouts and legal status of Belarusian political prisoner Nikolai Statkevich have remained unknown, illustrating the extreme form of uncertainty that arises when attempting to remain inside the country.

What is described here is not the continuation of repression in a legally formalized form, but the individual’s fall into a zone of total opacity, where the actions of the regime are not subject to verification and any mechanisms of legal and institutional protection cease to exist.

2.4. Limits of the Applicability of International Protection

Alongside the subordination of domestic legal mechanisms to the political will of the regime, another key limitation becomes evident - the limits of international protection. International human rights mechanisms are capable of documenting violations and providing them with legal assessment; however, they are unable to ensure a person's actual safety within the territory of a state that does not permit external oversight and does not comply with international decisions.

Under these conditions, international protection can function only after the individual has left the territory of the country. Within the state itself, it does not create conditions under which a "released" person could safely remain without facing the resumption of pressure.

This limitation is not related to inaction or insufficient engagement on the part of international actors. Rather, it reflects an objective limit of their capabilities in the context of a closed and repressive regime.

2.5. The Impossibility of Safe Presence within the Country as a Consequence of the Expulsion Mechanism

Within the framework of the phenomenon under consideration, the presence of a "released" person within the country is not envisaged. Release is used by the regime not to reintegrate the individual into life within the state, but as a stage in their forced removal beyond the country's borders.

The formal termination of deprivation of liberty does not restore legal status and does not create conditions for continued presence within the country. After release, the individual does not acquire a stable and recognized status under which their presence on the territory of the state is considered permissible.

Thus, the impossibility of safe presence within the country is a direct consequence of the operation of the expulsion mechanism. Release and subsequent removal form a single process, in which the termination of deprivation of liberty is used as a means of definitively removing the person from the state's territory.

2.6. Distortion of the Legal Logic of Punishment through Expulsion

In a criminal law system, the completion of a sentence signifies the end of the state's repressive impact and the termination of the individual's status as a convicted person. After serving a sentence or its lawful termination, the individual exits the scope of the judgment and is no longer subject to coercive measures in the absence of new legal grounds.

In the practice under consideration, this logic is disrupted. "Release" from a place of detention is used not for the legal completion of the sentence but as a means of forcibly removing the person from the country. Expulsion effectively substitutes the completion of punishment, while the individual's legal status remains unresolved.

This mechanism is most clearly manifested in the Belarusian context. A demonstrative example is the case of political prisoner Nikolai Statkevich. He was removed from a place of detention while his sentence was still ongoing and transported to the border with a demand to leave the territory of the state. After refusing expulsion, he was forcibly taken to an unknown location. Since September 2025, there has been no information regarding his whereabouts or legal status, including any information about his further fate.

This case demonstrates that refusal of expulsion does not result in the completion of punishment but leads to the complete loss of information about the individual.

Under the normal logic of criminal and international law, expulsion constitutes an additional repressive sanction that worsens the individual's position. It cannot be regarded as an acceptable alternative to the completion of punishment.

In the practice under consideration, however, the meaning of the measure changes. Expulsion remains repressive in nature but begins to be perceived as less destructive compared to refusal. Refusal results in total legal uncertainty, whereas consent to expulsion becomes the only means of terminating uncontrolled pressure.

The described mechanism represents a radical distortion of the very nature of repressive measures and of punishment as a legal institution.

This is not a matter of mitigation of the measure nor of the loss of its repressive character. What changes is not the substance of expulsion but the legal environment of its application: the regime destroys the conditions of legal certainty - the predictability of consequences, the formal fixation of status, and the possibility of procedural control - under which punishment must take a legally completed form.

From the perspective of international law, this has particular significance. In the configuration under consideration, refusal of expulsion entails more severe consequences than expulsion itself. Thus, a paradoxical construction emerges in which a coercive measure becomes the only way to avoid a more profound state of uncertainty.

As a result, law ceases to perform its function of limiting state violence. The termination of pressure is achieved not through the legal completion of punishment but through the physical removal of the individual beyond the jurisdiction of the state. Responsibility for such distortion of the legal framework lies with the regime that created and maintains this practice.

2.7. Why the Phenomenon Was Not Identified as an Independent Category for a Long Time

This phenomenon was not identified for a long time as an independent analytical category primarily because it does not leave the usual legal traces. Unlike deportation or expulsion, there are no formally issued decisions on removal or a direct prohibition on remaining in the country.

In the basic configuration, repression concludes with an outwardly neutral act - "release" - followed by the immediate forced removal of the person beyond the borders of the country. Under such an arrangement, what is taking place is easily perceived as the end of repression rather than its continuation in another form.

As a result, the main point is not recorded - the substitution of the logic of the legal completion of punishment. Removal is perceived as the termination of repression, whereas in fact it replaces a legally completed form of sanction.

The emphasis on mediation and negotiation formats leads to attention being focused on the fact of release and departure, while the coercive nature of removal from the country and the absence of the possibility to remain inside the country are not considered.

For this reason, the mechanism long remained outside the scope of systemic repressive analysis. It cannot be correctly identified through separate actions or documents. It becomes visible only when comparing two possible courses of conduct - departure and refusal to depart - and their consequences after "release."

3. Normative Model and the Limits of Its Applicability

This chapter describes the normative understanding of release and establishes the conditions under which it presupposes the real termination of repressive influence, as well as delineates the limits of applicability of this model under repressive regimes.

3.1. Normative Understanding of Release

In the normative understanding, release signifies the termination of a repressive status and the return of a person to the legal sphere. It presupposes the termination of the criminal-legal relationship between the state and the individual, as well as the state's refusal to pursue further

prosecution outside the procedures established by law.

A key element of such a model is the existence of a completed legal status, confirmed by the state and not allowing for arbitrary resumption of pressure. A released person ceases to be regarded as an object of repressive influence and obtains the possibility to live safely within the country, even if previously convicted in a politically motivated case.

Within the framework of the normative model, release presupposes:

- the legal completion of punishment on any ground provided by law, regardless of its form (serving the sentence in full, pardon, amnesty, parole, and other legal mechanisms);
- restoration of civil, political, social, and other rights restricted in connection with criminal prosecution;
- issuance of and unhindered access to all personal, identification, and title documents related to the person's identity, civil status, education, employment, and property;
- the possibility to remain safely within the territory of the country without the risk of repeated arbitrary or politically motivated deprivation of liberty in the absence of new unlawful acts;
- the exclusion of the practice of renewed pressure on the released person through courts, investigative bodies, or other state structures without proper legal grounds.

The decision of the released person to remain in the country or to leave it does not constitute grounds for altering his or her legal status.

3.2. The Real Boundary of the Applicability of the Normative Model

Under conditions of a closed and repressive regime, the normative model of release loses its practical applicability. This is due not to deficiencies in the legal norms themselves, but to the impossibility of their implementation within the existing political and legal environment.

First, internal legal mechanisms do not ensure the protection of rights and freedoms related to freedom of expression, freedom of speech, freedom of belief, and freedom of religion. In such situations, courts and other state bodies do not perform a protective function and are unable to provide a released person with real legal security.

Second, international human rights protection mechanisms have the capacity to record violations and provide them with legal assessment; however, they cannot ensure real protection within a state that does not allow external oversight and does not comply with international decisions.

As a result, refusal to leave the country becomes a source of risk. In practice, security and legal certainty become attainable only outside the territory of the state.

It is precisely at the point of divergence between the normative understanding of release and the impossibility of its implementation under a repressive regime that the phenomenon of forced expulsion through release arises.

4. Definition of the Phenomenon

Forced expulsion through release is a form of repressive practice in which the very act of release from places of detention is used by the regime as an instrument for removing a person beyond the borders of the state without the legal completion of their legal status and without the restoration of rights.

In circumstances where international protection mechanisms are unable to ensure safety within the state, such a practice functions as a mechanism for displacing the person beyond the regime's jurisdiction.

The defining characteristic is the absence of a real and safe alternative to continuing life within the country.

5. Structural Features of the Phenomenon

Forced expulsion through “release” is a phenomenon that arises under conditions in which “release” from places of detention does not mean the termination of repression and the return of a person to normal life.

Such “release” is not accompanied by the restoration of legal status or by real guarantees of security. It is used not to end repression, but as a mechanism for the forced removal of a person beyond the jurisdiction of the regime and for their exclusion from the observable legal field.

The described model is based on actually observed practice. The identified features reflect a specific mechanism documented in the examined cases.

Key features of the phenomenon:

1). Unfinished legal status after release.

An unfinished legal status is a condition in which release from places of detention occurs without the final closure of the criminal case and without the formal fixation of a completed procedural status of the person.

2). Impossibility of refusing departure in the basic configuration of the phenomenon

The basic configuration of the phenomenon of forced expulsion through release was formed under the conditions of the Belarusian regime. Within this configuration, refusal to depart after release is not permitted.

Refusal leads to repeated isolation and the effective disappearance of the person from the legal, public, and informational space. There is no official information about their whereabouts, procedural status, or legal position; the person becomes inaccessible to legal protection and public oversight.

Functional consequences of the mechanism:

1). Inapplicability of internal protection procedures

In the situation of forced expulsion through release, internal legal protection procedures cannot be used. “Release” is accompanied by the immediate removal of the person from the country which excludes the possibility of applying to a court, investigative authorities, or other state bodies.

Even in cases where such procedures are formally available, they are not capable of performing a protective function within the framework of the mechanism in question. “Release” is accompanied by the absence of a completed legal status and procedural fixation, as a result of which state authorities lack grounds to consider complaints as subject to protection.

The legal status of the person is not formally established, procedural decisions are not formalized, official information about their position is absent, which makes the use of internal remedies impossible.

2). Inapplicability of international protection mechanisms within the country

International human rights protection mechanisms are intended to record violations and provide their legal assessment, but they are not capable of changing the situation of a released person within a repressive regime.

Under conditions where the state does not allow external control and does not comply with international obligations, such mechanisms do not create real guarantees of security within the country.

As a result, international protection operates beyond the jurisdiction of the regime and does not influence the fate of the person who remains within the territory of the state.

3). Externalization of protection beyond the state

Real protection of the rights and security of a released person becomes possible only after leaving the control of the repressive regime.

Until that moment, the state retains full power over the person's situation, and any forms of protection remain unavailable.

In the model under consideration, security and the possibility of protection arise only after the person is outside the state. While they remain within the country, the available remedies are not capable of stopping the pressure and do not ensure the safe position of the released person.

The phenomenon of forced expulsion through release is reinforced by the following circumstances:

- the involvement of external intermediaries, whose role is limited to organizing departure and does not include demands for closing the criminal case, restoring legal status, or providing guarantees of security within the country;
- the use of the same operational scheme in cases of release and expulsion;
- the short time interval between release and expulsion;
- the shifting of responsibility for the person's further fate to external actors after their expulsion.

6. Mechanism of Reproduction

Forced expulsion through "release" is reproduced as a stable sequence of actions and conditions without the adoption of a specific decision on expulsion.

The typical scheme includes:

- deprivation of liberty;
- release without a completed legal status;
- impossibility of safely refusing expulsion;
- expulsion beyond the territory of the state as the only available scenario.

Within this mechanism, expulsion has no legal formalization and is not recorded as a legal decision of the state.

Release is used as a technical element that allows the removal of the person beyond the territory of the state without formalizing the expulsion and without terminating the repression.

7. Differentiation of the Phenomenon

Forced expulsion through "release" is not identical to other forms of movement of a person:

- it is not deportation, since there is no formally documented decision or order of expulsion;
- it is not voluntary emigration, since there is no real possibility to remain within the country;
- it is not humanitarian evacuation, since the source of the threat is the state itself, rather than external circumstances.

8. Criteria for Establishing and Logical Refutation of the Phenomenon

The phenomenon of forced expulsion through release is subject to verification through a set of observable indicators. This concerns not the intentions of the state and not subjective assessments, but a reproducible logic of consequences arising after the release of a person.

1). Verification Criteria

The phenomenon is established when the following structural conditions are simultaneously present:

- Absence of a completed legal status after "release."

The "release" is not accompanied by the final closure of the criminal case and the formal fixation of a completed procedural status of the person.

- Impossibility of safely refusing expulsion.
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An attempt to remain inside the country after “release” leads to immediate negative consequences that exclude a safe life.

When the above structural conditions are present, the following functional consequences of the mechanism are observed:

- Absence of effective protection within the state.

Internal legal mechanisms are not capable of preventing pressure or ensuring the restoration of the status of the “released” person.

- Cessation of the threat after expulsion.

After the removal of the person beyond the borders of the state, the risk of pressure, isolation, or disappearance ceases or significantly decreases.

The combination of these conditions and their consequences indicates that release does not terminate repression but becomes an element of the expulsion mechanism.

2). Conditions for Logical Refutation of the Phenomenon

The phenomenon cannot be established if, after release:

- the criminal case is definitively closed and the person’s status is legally completed;
- there is a possibility to remain inside the country without negative consequences;
- internal protection mechanisms are available and capable of genuinely changing the person’s situation;
- the threat persists after departure or does not depend on the person’s presence within the state.

In such cases, release does not perform a function of displacement and does not constitute the phenomenon under consideration.

8.1. Basic (Belarusian) Configuration of the Phenomenon

The basic configuration of the phenomenon was formed under the conditions of the Belarusian regime and served as the starting point of this concept.

In this configuration, the verification criteria are implemented in a rigid form:

- the release is not accompanied by the closure of the criminal case;
- refusal of expulsion leads to repeated isolation and the disappearance of the person from the legal and public space;
- internal remedies are not intended to protect the released person within the framework of this practice;
- the cessation of the threat occurs only after the actual removal of the person beyond the borders of the state.

At present, the phenomenon has been identified in one configuration. The Belarusian case demonstrates the most rigid of the observed forms and is used as the initial analytical reference point for further comparison.

9. External Intermediaries and the Limits of Protection.

Methodological Foundation of the Concept

Within the recorded practice, release is not accompanied by the completion of legal status and does not allow for a safe refusal to depart. Under these conditions, the participation of external intermediaries is limited to facilitating the departure of the “released” person beyond the borders of the country.

Sustainable protection within the state would require, simultaneously:

- the legal completion of status; a guaranteed possibility of safe residence;
- functioning internal protection mechanisms; access to monitoring and means of response in the event of renewed persecution. In the observed configuration, these conditions are absent.

Therefore, external actors do not possess the means to guarantee the legal status or physical security of the person within the jurisdiction of the regime. Their involvement does not restore the person's position within the state and does not protect against renewed pressure in the event of refusal to depart.

This limitation is not related to the intentions of the intermediaries, but to the structure of the mechanism itself, in which the cessation of threat is effectively linked to the removal of the person beyond the jurisdiction of the regime. Within the recorded practice, protection is realized outside the territory of the state.

Methodological Foundation of the Concept

The concept is based on an analysis of the Belarusian practice of releases accompanied by expulsion, as set out in the research report (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18444848>).

The present text does not reproduce the evidentiary base. The concept formalizes a model derived from the recorded empirical configuration and establishes the criteria for its application and refutation.

All conclusions regarding the structure of the mechanism, the role of actors, and the dynamics of the waves of releases are based on the corresponding research. The present text constitutes a theoretical generalization rather than a repetition of the evidentiary section.

10. Final Synthesis

Within the framework of the practice under consideration, release does not terminate repression but changes its form: it ceases to be the legal completion of prosecution and becomes an instrument of forced displacement of the person beyond the borders of the state.

11. Conclusion

The analysis demonstrates that, within the practice under consideration, release does not signify the termination of persecution. An individual leaves prison, yet their safety continues to depend on whether they leave the country.

Thus, release ceases to function as the final stage of punishment. It becomes a transitional phase after which pressure effectively ends only outside the state. This concept identifies the mechanism not through official statements or political interpretations, but through a recurring sequence of conditions and consequences. If, after release, the legal status remains unresolved, remaining in the country is unsafe, and the risk decreases only after departure, what occurs is not the termination of persecution but forced expulsion.

The model is derived from Belarusian practice and applies within the limits of this empirical basis. Should a consistent practice emerge in which release is accompanied by genuine completion of legal status and safety within the country, the conclusion would require revision.

Until such a case appears, release in the described configuration cannot be regarded as an independent termination of persecution, since its actual outcome is not the restoration of rights but the cessation of pressure only after leaving the country.